

NATALE VACALEBRE

“PER MAGGIOR DECORO DE’ NOSTRI PAESI”.

ANGELO MARIA D’ELCI BETWEEN BIBLIOPHILIA AND PATRIOTIC PRIDE

The history of book collecting has been significantly shaped by the contributions of early Italian collectors, whose profound influence has played a crucial role in the development of modern bibliophilia.¹ It is undeniable that Angelo Maria Pannocchieschi d’Elci (1754-1824) stands as the pioneering Italian intellectual who significantly advanced the discipline and expanded the horizons of the peninsula’s bibliophilic tradition to encompass a wide international perspective.² Originating from a Sienese aristocratic family that had relocated to Florence,³ d’Elci epitomized the cosmopolitan intellectual of the eighteenth century in many respects. After receiving a traditional home education mostly focused on the study of classical languages and literature, the young Angelo decided to dedicate himself to the study of modern languages, quickly mastering French, English, and German. This choice undoubtedly proved advantageous in his future career as a bibliophile.

In 1783, he embarked on his initial journeys to the European capitals, visiting Paris, Vienna, Prague, and Berlin. Five years later, d’Elci made his first visit to London, where he stayed for over four months until January 1789. Further travels, likely driven by his growing passion for rare books – and especially for incunabula, took him to Regensburg, Nuremberg, Bamberg, Frankfurt, and Munich. During this sort of reverse Grand Tour, d’Elci had the opportunity to visit some of the richest libraries of his time, undergoing a form of bibliographic training that led him to become one of the foremost incunabula scholars in Europe and one of the most distinguished connoisseurs of European rare book collections. In 1792, d’Elci himself stated that his passion for fifteenth-century printed editions had driven him to study firsthand the volumes housed in every library he visited. Although he had a solid knowledge of library catalogs, booksellers and auction catalogs, and specialized bibliographies, he always preferred to personally examine the copies he was interested in:

[...] le dirò sinceramente che le mie cognizioni in questo genere mi sembrano molto minori della fatica, del tempo e della spesa che mi costano. Le dirò solamente che ho continuato per de’ mesi a star per le scale come i paratori di chiesa, ogni mattina nelle più grandi biblioteche d’Europa e non mi sono mai fidato né di cataloghi stampati, né di quei delle vendite, né delle medesime biblioteche.

I will honestly tell you that my knowledge in this field seems to me much less than the effort, time, and expense it costs me. I will only tell you that for months I continued to stand on the stairs like church decorators, every morning in the largest libraries in Europe, and I have never trusted neither printed catalogs, nor those of sales, nor those of the libraries.⁴

This predisposition towards analytical bibliographic research defined his career as both a collector and a patriotic scholar. As we will see in the following pages, d’Elci was indeed the promoter of one of the most important book collecting projects of the modern age: the first

¹ Part of this research was funded by the *FILOL – Finding the Lost Library* project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (H2020-MSCA-IF-2022, grant agreement No 101062473).

² *La collezione di Angelo Maria d’Elci. Incunaboli ed edizioni rare*. Florence 1989; IDA GIOVANNA RAO: Per la biografia di Angelo Maria d’Elci. In: *Archivio storico italiano* 159 (1991), pp. 376-449.

³ Angelo was born as the second son to Marquess Ludovico Pannocchieschi d’Elci and Marchioness Lucrezia di Angelo Niccolini. Lacking access to substantial financial inheritance and to his father’s title, he affiliated himself with the Order of Saint John of Jerusalem in 1780. By 1782, Angelo had been designated a Knight of St. John, the formal noble title that subsequently defined his social identity within the contemporary societal circles. CARLO ANTONIO DE ROSA: *Notizie di alcuni cavalieri del Sacro Ordine Gerosolimitano illustri per lettere e belle arti*. Naples 1841, pp. 140-4.

⁴ Letter to Costantino Battini [1792], quoted from RAO (see note 1), p. 400. Unless otherwise specified all translations are mine.

collection of early printed editions of classics “ad uso e decoro pubblico” (for the public use and decorum) of a state of the peninsula.⁵

A European Bibliophile

Like many aristocrats of his time, d’Elci fell victim to the so-called *bibliomania* that swept across Europe from the late eighteenth century. This peculiar trend found remarkable success particularly in Great Britain, where the economic stability and prosperity of the Industrial Revolution allowed generations of nobles and wealthy bourgeoisie to build exquisite private book collections, mirrors of their social prestige.⁶ The substantial financial resources of British collectors were certainly not an advantage that a Tuscan nobility cadet like d’Elci could boast. Nevertheless, this did not prevent him from falling in love with the world of early printed books and successfully pursuing a grand collecting project for years: to create the most comprehensive European collection of fifteenth-century first editions of ancient Greek and Latin authors.

Collecting the early printed editions of the classics was not a goal motivated by mere scholarly whims. Like many Italian intellectuals of his time, d’Elci harbored certain literary aspirations in adulthood, joining the Accademia dell’Arcadia in 1777 and publishing several tragedies in the following years. However, his poetic career was quickly halted by negative reviews of his work, particularly by the poet Vittorio Alfieri, who criticized the Florentine scholar’s literary talents.⁷ Unable to rely on his literary skill to achieve social success, d’Elci leveraged his talents elsewhere, to provide his contemporaries and posterity with a testament to Italian cultural greatness.

D’Elci’s collecting project was shaped by the influence of the social and cultural policies of Grand Duke Leopold of Lorraine. In the vibrant cultural environment of eighteenth-century Florence, scholarly studies became tools contributing to the reformers of the Grand Duchy, turning into an instrument of political propaganda⁸. Within this bustling socio-political landscape, d’Elci developed his own concept of bibliography and book collecting. The moral and social renaissance of Leopold II’s Tuscany echoed that of the Medici’s Florence, an era in which the rediscovery and reevaluation of classical texts played a crucial role in the city’s progress. Collecting the first printed editions of classical works was tantamount to preserving the oldest testimonies of those almost forgotten texts that, thanks to the printing technology, could see the light after centuries of oblivion. Seen through the lens of the neo-Medicean renewal initiated by the Lorraine governors, d’Elci’s venture was effectively a mission equivalent to gathering and safeguarding the earliest testimonies of the renaissance of the *buone lettere* that occurred in Italy four hundred years prior. In other words, the idea of creating a library of only first editions of texts considered fundamental to human knowledge appeared as a new and original reflection of the enlightened reformism of Leopold II’s government.

⁵ D’Elci to Daniele Francesconi, Naples on January 12th 1817 (Rovigo, Archivio Civico, ms. Conc. 378/34, 2). The letter is partially transcribed in LUCIANA BIGLIAZZI: “Ad uso e decoro pubblico della mia patria Firenze”. Storia di una donazione: la collezione di Angelo Maria D’Elci e la biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana. In: *Rara volumina* 14-2 (2007), p. 65.

⁶ On the history of modern British collectors’ private libraries see MARK PURCELL: *The Country House Library*. New Haven and London 2017, pp. 162-5. On the phenomenon of *bibliomania* see the classic THOMAS FROGNALL DIBDIN: *Bibliomania; or Book Madness: A Bibliographical Romance, in Six Parts*. 2nd ed., London 1811; PHILIP CONNELL: Bibliomania: Book Collecting, Cultural Politics, and the Rise of Literary Heritage in Romantic Britain. In: *Representations*, 71 (2000), pp. 24-47.

⁷ EMILIO BOGANI: Vittorio Alfieri e Angiolo d’Elci amici e rivali. In: *Annali alfieriani* 4 (1985), pp. 89-127.

⁸ EMMANUELLE CHAPRON : *Ad utilità pubblica: politique des bibliothèques et pratiques du livre à Florence au XVIII^e siècle*. Genève 2009.

Assembling such a collection was certainly not an easy task, especially considering that d'Elci, as previously mentioned, had only a modest income to rely on. However, his shrewdness and intelligence led him to build a dense and solid network of high-ranking friendships, which enabled him, at different levels, to advance his project.

Among his most noteworthy alliances was his friendship with Angelo Maria Bandini (1726-1803), librarian of the Marucelliana and Laurentian libraries⁹, and more significantly, his bond with Prince Ferdinand III of Habsburg-Lorraine (1769-1824). The latter relationship proved to be of immense value, granting d'Elci permission to access the treasured repositories of Florentine libraries. This privilege facilitated a unique approach to building his collection, employing a mix of exchanges and, at times, outright removals of books—activities endorsed by his political protectors, thus skirting the boundaries of legality.

As d'Elci's project evolved, he broadened the scope of his collection to include first editions of Italian authors and those printed in the 16th century. Alongside works of great names of classical literature like Cicero, Polybius, Pliny, and Euripides, there came those of “modern classics” like Dante, Petrarch, Erasmus, and Pietro Bembo.¹⁰

By 1792, d'Elci deemed his collection almost complete. Out of gratitude to the Lorraine family, who had supported his collecting endeavors, he offered it as a gift to the Tuscan government. The d'Elci collection was officially incorporated into the Imperial Laurentian Library in 1818. However, due to several delays, the books were not physically transferred to the library until 1841, seventeen years after d'Elci's death. A special Tribune was built to house the 1,199 first editions and 8 manuscripts he had donated to his country.¹¹

The d'Elci collection

When d'Elci's volumes were delivered to the Tuscan authorities, they constituted a collection unparalleled in Europe. The only other incunabula collections, in terms of first editions of the classics, that could be compared to it were those created in England by George Spencer, 2nd Earl Spencer (1758-1834), and George Spencer-Churchill, 5th Duke of Marlborough (1766-1840).¹²

D'Elci's visionary intent behind curating such a collection was not merely to amass books but to engage in the burgeoning movement of modern European bibliophilia, with the specific aim of rejuvenating and modernizing the antique Italian book collecting tradition. This endeavor was characterized by an inclusive approach that embraced both Italian and non-Italian early printed editions, thus broadening the geographical, cultural and historical scope of his collection.

Contrary to the practices of many European aristocratic collectors, who might have relied on their wealth to enrich their libraries, d'Elci's strategy for building his collection was specifically connected to his skills as a bibliographer. He engaged in an intensive activity of book exchange, procuring his most prized volumes from major European cultural hubs such as

⁹ ROSARIO PINTAUDI: *Un erudito del Settecento: Angelo Maria Bandini*. Messina 2002.

¹⁰ For a complete account of d'Elci's collection at the time of the donation see the *Catalogo dei libri dal Conte Angiolo Maria D'Elci, donati all'Imperiale e Real Libreria Mediceo Laurenziana*. Florence 1826.

¹¹ BIGLIAZZI (see note 4).

¹² ANTHONY LISTER: The Althorp Library of Second Earl Spencer, Now in the John Rylands University Library of Manchester: Its Formation and Growth. In: *Bulletin of the John Rylands University Library of Manchester* 71-2 (1989), pp. 67-86; PETER H. REID: “The Finest Private Library in Europe»: A Brief Study of the Bibliophile Spencers of Althorp”, *Library History*, 14-1 (1998), pp. 65-71. A detailed description of the Duke of Marlborough's dispersed collection can be found in *White Knights Library: Catalogue of that Distinguished and Celebrated Library ... Which Will Be Sold by Auction*. London 1819.

Milan, Vienna, Berlin, Paris, and London. Through this exchanges scheme, d'Elci not only expanded his collection but also forged connections with librarians, booksellers and collectors across Europe, thereby gaining access to the catalogs of the most prestigious libraries and book auctions of the continent. This method allowed him to acquire valuable exemplars for his collection of first editions of *quattrocentisti*, trading them not for monetary compensation but in exchange for books that were absent from the collections of his fellow “bibliomaniacs”. He himself stated it more than once, over the course of his extensive correspondence with Marquis Francesco Taccone, which will be discussed in more detail in the following pages:

Io gli ho replicato che non potevo immediatamente rispondere, perché ancora io dipendevo da altra risposta, e che quanto al mio Q. Curzio, prima edizione duplicata, l'avrei dato, qualora mi fosse stato valutato il prezzo conveniente, in libri però, non in contanti, perché io non mi privo neppur de' miei doppi a contanti, ma solamente per procurare per via di cambi altri articoli, che convengono alla mia raccolta.

I replied to him that I could not immediately respond because I was still waiting for another answer. As for my Q. Curtius, of which I own two copies of the first edition, I would have given it away, had I been offered the right price, in books, however, not in cash, because I do not part with even my duplicates for cash, but only to acquire through exchange other items that suit my collection.¹³

In scholarly terms, d'Elci was a consummate professional in the realm of early printed books. His expertise encompassed a thorough understanding of printing techniques and the material structures of incunabula and, in general, of early printed editions. His approach to collecting was methodical and analytical. As previously mentioned, he meticulously studied each volume, frequented both public and private libraries to examine books firsthand, and undertook comparative analyses of the items within his and other European collections. Such diligence underscores d'Elci's commitment to not just collecting books but also comprehending their historical and cultural significance, their physical characteristics, and their place within the broader narrative of European intellectual history.

The quest for the best copies drove d'Elci's bibliophilic pursuits. He sought after books that had to be in immaculate condition, with wide margins and devoid of any handwritten annotations – volumes that retained their original “purity” as they had left the printer's workshop. This pursuit was not merely driven by a collector's desire for aesthetically pleasing objects. It was deeply rooted in the values of modern European bibliophilia and the quest for textual purity. Like many other bibliophiles of his time, d'Elci was influenced by the *Avvertenze necessarie e profittevoli a' bibliotecari e agli amatori de' buoni libri* (1756). This was a successful pamphlet by Abbot Gaetano Volpi (1689-1761) that educated generations of collectors and booksellers in the pursuit of the *immaculate* book, which was to be restored to its supposed typographic purity through the practice of chemical washing¹⁴. Such ideals guided D'Elci's selections, reflecting his understanding of the book as a cultural artifact and a testament to the intellectual endeavors of the past.

Over approximately three decades, lacking the vast financial means of France's and England's major aristocratic book collectors, d'Elci managed to create one of Europe's most remarkable incunabula collections, and undoubtedly the most extraordinary in Italy. D'Elci himself lamented the absence of a proper international bibliophilic movement in his homeland. Through his efforts, the nobleman sought to elevate the Italian book collecting tradition to a level commensurate with the international standards of his time.

D'Elci's extensive travels across Europe afforded him an unparalleled view of the bibliographic marvels hosted in the opulent residences of the French, English, and German nobility. These explorations allowed him to witness firsthand the most significant collections

¹³ *Lettere bibliografiche del cavaliere Angelo Maria d'Elci; con brevi note di Vito Capialbi*. Messina 1851, p. 39.

¹⁴ GAETANO VOLPI: *Avvertenze utili e necessarie agli amatori de' buoni libri* (1756). Milano 2006.

held by these wealthy and powerful nations. The libraries he visited were a reflection of those countries' well-being, cultural richness, and power. In contrast, Italy, fragmented by the lack of political unity, remained tethered to its economic and cultural glorious past, yet it grappled with a present marked by division and provincialism. Through his collection and scholarly endeavors, d'Elci aspired to bridge this divide, contributing to the cultural and intellectual revitalization of Italy within the European context.

The "Lettere Bibliografiche"

The *Lettere Bibliografiche* are a collection of 24 epistles that D'Elci wrote between 1803 and 1807 to Marquis Francesco Taccone. Taccone was a high official in the Kingdom of Naples, a loyalist to King Ferdinand I of Bourbon. Besides being a significant dignitary at the Neapolitan court, Taccone was also an avid but inexperienced bibliophile. Perhaps through the Duke of Cassano Serra, another prominent Neapolitan collector, D'Elci soon made contact with him and offered to help and guide him in the world of international book collecting.¹⁵

Published in 1851 by Vito Capialbi, a Calabrian bibliophile and Taccone's nephew, the *Lettere* were enthusiastically reviewed by Pierre Gustave Brunet in the *Bullettin du Bibliophile* in 1855. They serve both as a manual of incunabula studies and a practical guide for emerging bibliophiles. D'Elci's correspondence with Taccone is pragmatic, focusing primarily on bibliographic matters.¹⁶ The *Lettere* reveal D'Elci's enthusiasm for assisting Taccone, who owns a valuable yet obscure collection of early editions of classics where perhaps some interesting volumes for d'Elci's own library might be hidden. However, the most interesting aspect of the Letters is that they show exactly D'Elci's conception of bibliophilia: a blend of aristocratic and patriotic values centered on book collecting as a tool to revitalize Italian bibliographic and literary culture.

In an early letter dated April 30, 1803, D'Elci engages in a debate with Taccone concerning the primacy of the printed editions of the classics – specifically, whether the first and finest were produced by the Germans or the Italians. This debate arises from a question Taccone had previously raised. The necessity of this discussion underscores the cultural provincialism prevalent among members of the Neapolitan court at the time. Taccone, deeply rooted in the prestige of Italian Renaissance literature, fails to differentiate between literary and technical achievements in book production. His limited understanding of book history leads him to erroneously believe that the earliest German editions were confined to liturgical and devotional materials, thereby asserting that Italians maintained supremacy in producing both the earliest and the superior editions of classical texts rediscovered during the Renaissance.

D'Elci, with patience, clarifies to Taccone that, from a historical-typographical perspective, the so-called primacy of classical editions belongs to German printers. He points out that Italy did not have printing presses until the 1460s. Furthermore, he credits the Germans with the invention of movable type and its subsequent introduction in Italy through itinerant printers. After listing several Latin works published in Germany prior to the advent of printing in Italy, D'Elci advises his noble yet misinformed correspondent that making inaccurate claims

¹⁵ VINCENZO TROMBETTA: *Collezionismo e bibliofilia a Napoli tra Sette e Ottocento: un ritratto epistolare*. Macerata 2020; VINCENZO TROMBETTA: La libreria del marchese Taccone e le vicende della Biblioteca Gioacchina (1812-1815). In: *Rendiconti della Accademia di Archeologia Lettere e Belle Arti di Napoli* 64 (1993-1994), pp. 15-75; GIANCARLO PETRELLA: Prime note per la destratificazione di un giacimento librario. Gli incunaboli della Biblioteca Universitaria di Napoli e la mancata consegna della Tacconiana. In: *Gli Incunaboli della Biblioteca Universitaria di Napoli. Catalogo*. Ed. GIANCARLO PETRELLA. Rome 2022, pp. 17-89.

¹⁶ PIERRE GUSTAVE BRUNET: Correspondance retrospective. In: *Bullettin du Bibliophile*, 1 (1855), pp. 269-70.

about such primacy not only fails to honor Italy but also tarnishes its reputation. He argues that such assertions could lead European bibliophiles to view Italian collectors as inferior scholars, lacking the resources and networks to acquire these editions. Therefore, D'Elci suggests that the best course of action is to diligently seek and acquire the earliest German editions, thereby assembling incunabula and rare book collections that are both unique and comprehensive, thus enhancing Italian glory in the eyes of the world:

Ella vede dopo di ciò che gl'Italiani dicendo che la Germania non ha dato altro che libri ecclesiastici, invece di crescere l'onore dell'Italia lo diminuirebbero, facendo supporre che in Italia non si conoscesse l'esistenza di tali edizioni, e che non si abbiano i mezzi per procurarsele. A me dunque sembra maggior patriottismo il procurarle all'Italia, che il dire che non sono prime edizioni, e che valgono poco. Diamo a tutti quel che loro è dovuto, e credo che in questa giustizia noi altri Italiani ci guadagnamo infinitamente perché è tanto quel che gli altri paesi debbono all'Italia, che ci può bastare, ed anco avanzare, senza usurpare quel poco che agli altri è dovuto.

You understand that Italians, by saying that Germany has only produced ecclesiastical books, instead of increasing Italy's honor, would diminish it by implying that in Italy we are unaware of the existence of these editions, and that we do not have the means to acquire them. It seems to me, therefore, more patriotic to procure them for Italy than to say that they are not first editions, and that they are of little value. Let's give to everyone what is due, and I believe that in this justice we Italians gain immensely, because there are so many things that other countries owe to Italy, which can suffice for us, and even advance, without usurping the little that is due to others.¹⁷

These lines encapsulate D'Elci's bibliophile-patriotic philosophy, highlighting his drive towards the internationalization of Italy's culturally and socially provincial states. D'Elci's words carry a deep social metaphor, reflecting Italy's deficiency in private rare book collections, akin to its lack of formidable armies – a symbol of cultural, economic, and political dominance that nations like England and France have long established. His perspective, though niche, realistically connects bibliophilia with an aristocratic form of patriotism that is nostalgic yet forward-looking. D'Elci aspires to unify Italian intellectuals and nobility under a new cultural banner rooted in Florentine Renaissance humanism. D'Elci posits that Italy urgently needs to establish new bibliophile collections to rejuvenate and elevate its culture on the global stage. He argues against clinging to past glories and advocates for a proactive engagement with contemporary realities and openness to the cultural advancements and innovations of other nations. This approach, he suggests, is essential for reviving Italy's cultural prominence.

Despite D'Elci's elucidations, Taccone, firmly entrenched in his aristocratic and parochial views, persists in his beliefs. In a letter that has not survived, he reasserts his conviction that the Italians surpassed the Germans in the literary contributions of the fifteenth century, and insists that Italian editions of the classics are superior and thus more desirable. Faced once more with Taccone's stubborn stance, D'Elci is compelled to exercise patience and reiterate his points. In a letter dated June 10, 1803, he once again clarifies that modern bibliophilia should not be confused with philology; typography, he stresses, is a mechanical technique, not a literary art. He reasserts the technical primacy of German printers in the early history of printing, arguing that the most coveted first editions of classical texts are those produced in Germany. He acknowledges that while Italian typographic execution might be technically superior, this was often under the direction of German craftsmen, further underscoring the foundational role of German innovation in the field. This distinction, D'Elci argues, is crucial for understanding the true value and significance of early printed works in the broader context of bibliophilia.

Quanto al parallelo fra la tipografia di Germania e quella d'Italia non so se possa farsi: ma seppure si può fare, credo che bisogna premettere molte distinzioni. Primeramente conviene separare affatto in tal questione l'arte dello stampare, dalle arti liberali, nelle quali, dopo la Grecia antica, la nostra Italia avrà sempre il primato. Ma l'arte tipografica è un semplice meccanismo, né può, né deve mai mettersi in concorso con la letteratura. Gli Italiani dal Petrarca fino al Tasso, cioè per duecento e più anni sono stati i veri maestri della vera letteratura, senza neppur

¹⁷ *Lettere bibliografiche* (see note 12), p. 9.

nominare i loro predecessori, cioè gli antichi Romani, di cui siamo i veri discepoli ed eredi. Hanno avuto uomini grandi anco gli oltramontani in belle lettere, ma non tali, né tanti. [...] Ma non si tratta, come dissi, di letteratura, né di belle arti; si tratta di tipografia, e di meccanica: e come tale bisogna pur confessare, che il primo pregio è sempre quello dell'invenzione, e l'invenzione è di Germania: i Tedeschi la portarono in Italia, ed i primi ad eseguirla ed anco a perfezionarla in Italia furono Oltramontani [...] L'aver dato l'Italia più classici nel 1400 di quel che ne abbia dati la Germania, è una gloria che appartiene alla letteratura, e non già alla tipografia, poiché per lo stampatore è l'istessa cosa lo stampare un Salterio, o un Virgilio [...] sicché, considerando tal'arte come puramente meccanica, come infatti lo è, non si può negare, che l'invenzione primiera, e l'estrema, e l'ultima perfezione appartenga agli Oltramontani: sicché, facendo quella distinzione che deve farsi fra letteratura e tipografia, fra arte meccanica, e bell'arte, credo, che facilmente ci troveremo d'accordo.

Regarding the comparison between the printing industry in Germany and that in Italy, I am not sure if it can be made; but even if it can, I believe that many distinctions must be made first. Primarily, it is appropriate to completely separate the art of printing from the liberal arts, in which, after ancient Greece, our Italy will always hold the lead. However, the typographic art is a mere mechanism and cannot, nor should it ever, compete with literature. The Italians, from Petrarch to Tasso, i.e., for more than two hundred years, have been the true masters of true literature, without even mentioning their predecessors, i.e., the ancient Romans, of whom we are the true disciples and heirs. The people from beyond the Alps had great men in literature as well, but not as many or as notable. [...] But as I said, the matter at hand is not literature or fine arts; it is about typography and mechanics: and as such, we must admit that the first merit always lies in the invention, and the invention is from Germany: the Germans brought it to Italy, and the first to execute it and even to perfect it in Italy were the people from beyond the Alps [...] Italy having produced more classics in the 1400s than Germany did, is a glory that belongs to literature, and not to typography, since for the printer, it is the same to print a Psalter or a Virgil [...] hence, considering such art as purely mechanical, as indeed it is, one cannot deny that the original invention, the extreme, and the ultimate perfection belong to the people from beyond the Alps: hence, making that distinction that must be made between literature and typography, between mechanical art and fine art, I believe that we will easily find ourselves in agreement.¹⁸

To truly elevate the status of an Italian state and its cultural heritage through bibliophilic collections, D'Elci argues that it is essential to acquire non-Italian editions of classical texts. He reinforces his argument by appealing to the Neapolitan pride of his correspondent. D'Elci tactfully undermines the prestige of the collection owned in Naples by the Duke of Cassano Serra, which is reputed to be among the best in Europe. He reveals to Taccone that, in reality, this collection is significantly inferior not only to his own and that of Lord Spencer, but also to other notable English collections, such as those of the Duke of Marlborough and Clayton Mordaunt Cracherode.¹⁹ With a strategic use of flattery, D'Elci encourages Taccone, asserting that with his guidance, the Marquis could indeed surpass all European bibliophiles. He paints a vision of establishing a collection of first editions in Italy that would be unparalleled and long-deserved, thereby securing Italy's place as a key player in the global arena of bibliophilia. This, D'Elci suggests, would not only honor the Italian peninsula but also fulfill a cultural imperative, showcasing Italy's rich intellectual legacy and its lively contemporary bibliophilic endeavors.

In subsequent letters, D'Elci embarks on educating Taccone in the intricacies of incunabula studies and bibliophily, transforming their correspondence into a specialized tutorial. In a letter dated June 15, 1803, he instructs Taccone on how to identify and date editions that lack typographic information (*sine notis*). D'Elci posits that these editions are often older than their dated counterparts and emphasizes their crucial bibliophilic value, particularly noting that no collection of first editions of the classics can be considered complete without them. He specifically points out the importance of acquiring German editions, given their historical significance in the early stages of typographic development.²⁰

In a follow-up letter sent on June 26, D'Elci discusses strategies for procuring these valuable volumes both within Italy and internationally. He expresses a strong preference for foreign booksellers, particularly praising those from England and France for their expertise and

¹⁸ *Lettere bibliografiche* (see note 12), p. 19.

¹⁹ ADINA DAVIS: Clayton Mordaunt Cracherode. In: *The Book Collector* 23 (1974), p. 339-54 and pp. 489-505.

²⁰ *Lettere bibliografiche* (see note 12), pp. 27-31.

ability to fairly price books. In contrast, D'Elci is scathingly critical of Italian book dealers, whom he describes as highly unprofessional. These individuals, according to D'Elci, are often mere amateurs like lawyers, men of letters, or librarians with no genuine understanding of bibliography and frequently attempt to deceive their clients. Despite this harsh critique, he acknowledges the necessity of dealing with these traders, as they are often the only accessible sources for early editions produced in the Italian peninsula:

Sono persone anfibie ora dilettanti, ora collettori, ora negozianti, e questa incertezza della loro professione imbarazza moltissimo, ma fuori che in Francia o in Inghilterra chi cerca simil genere di libri, bisogna che s'indirizzi a persone di questa specie, che sono Bibliotecari, Avvocati, Letterati, Cavalieri, ma tutt'in generale sono figure molto amanti del proprio interesse. Secondo me questa è la parte più disgustosa che s'incontri nel raccogliere tali libri. Bisogna farsi mangiare, burlare, tradire, perdere un'infinità di tempo senza concludere nulla, e intanto bisogna dissimular tutto per non perdere il corrispondente comunque sia, perchè senza corrispondenti non si trovano libri, e non perdere mai la pazienza e l'assiduità perchè altrimenti non si continua la collezione.

These are 'amphibious' people, sometimes amateurs, sometimes collectors, sometimes merchants, and this uncertainty of their profession is very bothersome. But unfortunately, apart from in France or England, those who seek this type of book must address themselves to this kind of people, who are librarians, lawyers, men of letters, minor aristocrats; but overall, these are people who only care about their own interests. In my opinion, this is the most disgusting part of the career of a rare books collector. One must allow oneself to be eaten, to be duped, to be betrayed, to lose an infinity of time without concluding anything. And in the meantime, one must act as if nothing happened, so as not to lose the correspondent, because without correspondents one does not find the books; and one must never lose patience and constancy, because otherwise, it will be impossible to continue building the collection.²¹

This letter poignantly captures his frustration as a collector and intellectual faced with a profound paradox within early 19th-century Italy. Despite an abundance of rare volumes flooding the market – a consequence of the suppression of religious orders by the Pope in 1773, the Grand Duke of Tuscany in 1785, and the Napoleonic governments in 1808 – Italy sorely lacks professional booksellers equipped with the necessary bibliographic expertise and the ethical standards required for handling such precious commodities. D'Elci's correspondence reveals not only his disdain for the provincialism that he perceives among Italian book dealers but also his broader aspirations for Italy. He envisions a future where the peninsula can match the cultural and possibly even the economic standards of other European nations he has admired during his travels. This vision extends beyond mere bibliophily; it encompasses a desire for an intellectual and moral advancement in Italian society, aligning with the more sophisticated and honest book trade practices he has observed abroad.

The stark contrast between D'Elci and Taccone is palpable throughout their correspondence. Taccone, a Bourbon aristocrat with intellectual leanings, clings to a narrow, nationally confined view of culture and literature. D'Elci, representing a Europeanist perspective, urges him to shed his parochial views and embrace the broader cultural landscapes of neighboring countries to truly ascend to the rank of a bibliophile with a collection of international repute. D'Elci, despite his roots in the conservative Tuscan aristocracy, emerges as a cosmopolitan figure. His extensive travels and intellectual pursuits have equipped him with a profound understanding of the world beyond the Italian peninsula. His engagements have not only enriched his linguistic and intellectual repertoire but have also allowed him to establish a network of relationships with scholars and collectors across Europe. This background led him to emphasize the importance of incorporating and appreciating external influences to enhance Italy's cultural and intellectual standing. This global perspective sets him apart from many of his contemporaries, who remain tethered to the nostalgic recollection of Italy's historical grandeur.

²¹ *Lettere bibliografiche* (see note 12), p. 35-6.

D'Elci's connection with Lord Spencer, one of his most significant foreign correspondents, exemplifies the rich intellectual exchange that characterized his interactions with fellow bibliophiles. Lord Spencer, known for having assembled one of the richest collections of incunabula and rare books of the era, and as a founder of the prestigious Roxburghe Club, greatly admired D'Elci's bibliographic expertise.²² Their correspondence, likely initiated in the 1790s, revolved around complex bibliographic topics. Thomas Frognall Dibdin, Spencer's bibliographer and librarian, noted that Spencer regarded D'Elci as the foremost bibliographer on the continent and his equal in technical knowledge.²³ Spencer's high regard for D'Elci was further solidified upon visiting D'Elci's collection in Naples, which he found exceptionally compelling, even noting specific works absent from his own collection that he needed to acquire. This mutual respect and exchange of insights not only enriched both their collections but also underscored the depth of their scholarly pursuits.

In the *Lettere*, d'Elci strategically leverages his relationship with Lord Spencer to influence Taccone, urging him to expand his bibliophilic perspective and embrace a more global approach to collecting early printed books. In a letter dated July 6, D'Elci shares with Taccone how he and Spencer navigated dealings with booksellers, particularly in terms of pricing strategies. He explains that booksellers often set prices based on a comparison between the final price of a book sold at the Duke de la Valliere's 1784 auction and recent English auctions.²⁴ Significant discrepancies between these prices led booksellers to lean towards the higher price, while collectors like Spencer and D'Elci would opt for a median value, a strategy that combined astuteness with fair dealing:

Non sarà difficile il convenire, perchè ci sono le sue regole già fisse e stabilite, ed adattate generalmente in tali contratti di prime edizioni. Si determina il prezzo del libro, secondo il prezzo a cui è arrivato alla vendita del Duca de la Valiere, secondo quello delle vendite pubbliche d'Inghilterra. Quando fra il prezzo de la Valiere, e quello d'Inghilterra, ci è una differenza considerabile ; i negozianti si regolano sul maggiore, i collettori scelgono il prezzo medio fra i due prezzi, e questa è la regola più giusta e più discreta, e quella che sempre si è praticata fra Mylord Spencer e me.

It will not be difficult to agree, as there are already fixed and established rules, which are generally adapted for contracts involving first editions. The price of the book is determined based on the price it reached at the Duke de la Valiere's sale, and that of public sales in England. When there is a significant difference between the price at la Valiere's and that in England, dealers regulate themselves by the higher price, while collectors choose the median price between the two. This is the fairest and most prudent rule, and it is the one that has always been practiced between Lord Spencer and myself.²⁵

The insights provided by D'Elci in this letter are invaluable for understanding the historical development of book collecting, particularly the evaluation methods that prominent European collectors employed from the late eighteenth to the early nineteenth century. The economic aspect of book collecting is intricate and arguably one of the most challenging facets a collector must navigate. Mastery over the valuation and negotiation at auctions and private sales is essential for assembling and expanding a meaningful collection.

During the golden age of bibliomania, fueled by the industrial boom in the most developed nations, considerable capital flowed into the acquisition of rare early printed volumes, necessitating a reliable method to guide expenditure on such purchases. The auction of the La Valliere library became a landmark in the history of book collecting, not only because of the extraordinary volume of rare books it brought to market but also as it set a major precedent in the valuation of rare books in the Western world. The sale generated a total of

²² The Roxburghe Club was founded after the sale in 1812 of the enormous library of the Duke of Roxburghe: *A catalogue of the library of the late John, Duke of Roxburghe*. London 1812.

²³ THOMAS FROGNALL DIBDIN: *Reminiscences of a Literary Life*. vol. 1, London 1836, p. 539.

²⁴ DOMINIQUE COQ: Le parangon du bibliophile français: le duc de la Vallière et sa collection. In: *Histoire des bibliothèques françaises. II: Les bibliothèques sous l'Ancien régime 1530-1789*. Ed. CLAUDE JOLLY. Paris 1988, pp. 316-31.

²⁵ *Lettere bibliografiche* (see note 12), pp. 45-6.

464,677 *livres*. At the auction, international booksellers and librarians such as Tilliard, Molini, and Payne participated, purchasing volumes for renowned European collectors like Bolongaro-Crevenna, Lord Spencer, the Grand Duke of Tuscany, Count de Rewiczky, and Thomas Grenville.²⁶ The auction attracted Europe's most affluent and prominent collectors, and the prices achieved for the duke's exquisite volumes were meticulously recorded in auction catalogs. These catalogs became essential tools, circulating among collectors and antiquarian booksellers across Europe and serving as benchmarks for pricing rare volumes.

D'Elci's accounts provide a rare contemporary insight into the significance of this event and its profound impact on the practices of European bibliophilia and the antiquarian book trade. His mention of using recent British auction results as a secondary reference point for price setting further illuminates the dynamics of the international market during the Napoleonic era. This practice underpinned a systematic approach to book valuation that would influence the trade well into the late nineteenth century.

In his correspondence with Taccone, D'Elci underscores the laborious and often thankless task of negotiating with booksellers, a necessary endeavor for any serious bibliophile. He emphasizes the importance of extending beyond the local market and engaging with international sellers and networks to truly enrich a collection. This point highlights the global dimension of sophisticated book collecting and poses a challenge to Taccone, testing his willingness and ability to operate on this broader stage.

Taccone appears receptive to D'Elci's guidance, expressing profound gratitude for the insights gleaned from the letters, which he regards as a comprehensive treatise on early German publishing—a testament to D'Elci's expertise and bibliographic knowledge. Pleased by this response, D'Elci writes back on July 22, expressing his heartfelt hope that his inadvertent treatise will not only benefit Taccone but also enhance Italian bibliographic culture more broadly. D'Elci's commitment to elevating Italian bibliophilia goes beyond mere advice; he resolves to intensify his efforts in acquiring ancient first editions from Germany, noting the scarcity of such works in Italian collections:

Mi lusingo che mettendo insieme tutte le mie lettere intorno alle antiche edizioni tedesche, ed a quelle senza data, ella avrà un piccolo trattato bibliografico, che servirà di qualche schiarimento in questa materia, e che non sarà affatto inutile alla nostra Italia, ove quella parte di scienza bibliografica, che riguarda le antiche edizioni oltramontane, non è stata tanto coltivata, quanto quella che appartiene all'italiane edizioni. Né ciò poteva agevolmente farsi per la scarsità in cui è l'Italia di tali edizioni straniere. Perciò, se Dio mi dà vita, pazienza e danari, raccoglierò qualche cosa anco in questo genere per maggior decoro, ed istruzione de' nostri paesi.

I pride myself that by gathering all my letters on the old German editions and the undated editions, you will have a small bibliographic treatise, which will serve to better elucidate this matter, and which will not be at all useless to our Italy, where this part of bibliographic science concerning the old editions from beyond the Alps has not been as cultivated as that which pertains to Italian editions. This could not easily be done either because of the rarity, in Italy, of these foreign editions. Therefore, if God gives me life, patience, and money, I will also collect something of this sort for the greater decorum and education of our countries.²⁷

This decision reflects a strategic and passionate approach to remedying a significant cultural gap, underscoring his belief in the power of exemplary collections to inspire and transform national bibliographic standards.

D'Elci's almost pedagogical efforts to introduce Taccone to the universe of international bibliophilia will bear fruit. The collection of the Neapolitan marquis will indeed become one of the most famous of the Bourbon kingdom and will be a destination for numerous European

²⁶ COQ (see note 23).

²⁷ *Lettere bibliografiche* (see note 12), pp. 45-6.

intellectuals eager to peruse the rare and precious volumes collected, in part, thanks to the advice of his Tuscan consultant.

Angelo Maria d'Elci emerges as a pivotal figure in the European bibliographic landscape between the decline of the Ancien Régime and the Napoleonic era. His dedication to collecting the first printed editions of classical texts transcends mere bibliomania, evolving into a patriotic endeavor. D'Elci viewed his collection as not just an assembly of books but as a gathering of the earliest material witnesses to the greatest achievements of human thought—classical literature. This endeavor was particularly significant given that Italy, unlike France, Germany, and England, lacked comprehensive public and private collections that included incunabula from across Europe.

D'Elci's approach to collecting was revolutionary within Italy, where the bibliophilic culture was predominantly insular, focused mainly on Italian typographic outputs. His break from this provincial mindset not only positioned him ideologically but also practically as Italy's first true bibliologist. His donation of a collection of classical and vernacular texts to the Biblioteca Laurenziana represented the first collection of international incunabula in Italy, setting a precedent for future Italian collectors before the nation's unification.

Recognized as the foremost Italian bibliographer of his time, D'Elci also served as a trusted bibliographic consultant. His *Bibliographical Letters* remains a seminal published record of his bibliologic acumen, bibliographic knowledge, and his European vision of book collecting. The full extent of D'Elci's impact on modern bibliophilia and analytical bibliography is yet to be fully appreciated, primarily due to the scattered and uncatalogued state of his papers across various repositories in Italy and Europe. The scholarly community eagerly anticipates more comprehensive studies that could consolidate and delve into his extensive archives, promising insights into his role and influence in the evolution of book collecting and the intellectual culture of his time. This further study could illuminate not only the breadth of D'Elci's contributions but also the depth of his philosophical and cultural insights, which continue to resonate within the bibliophilic and scholarly worlds.